

LEVERAGING BRANDING STRATEGIES TO INCREASE COMPETITIVENESS IN SMALL BUSINESSES

Kabulov Murodjon

Teacher of Collegium Humanum

Warsaw management university

Andijan branch

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11005221>

Annotation. *In this article explores the vital role of branding strategies in enhancing the competitiveness of small business entities. By delving into various facets of branding – from crafting a compelling brand identity to building brand equity and fostering brand loyalty and – we will uncover how small businesses can leverage branding as a strategic tool to differentiate themselves, attract customers, and thrive in a crowded marketplace.*

Keywords: *competitive, market share, brand awareness, positivism, interpretivism, trustworthiness, effectiveness, enhance, sustainability.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье исследуется жизненно важная роль стратегии брендинга в повышении конкурентоспособности субъектов малого бизнеса. Углубляясь в различные аспекты брендинга – от создания убедительной идентичности бренда до создания капитала бренда и повышения лояльности к бренду – мы узнаем, как малые предприятия могут использовать брендинг как стратегический инструмент для дифференциации себя, привлечения клиентов и процветания на переполненном рынке.*

Ключевые слова: *конкуренция, доля рынка, узнаваемость бренда, позитивизм, интерпретативизм, надежность, эффективность, повышение, устойчивость.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada kichik biznes sub'ektlarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda brending strategiyalarining muhim roli o'rganiladi. Brendlashning turli qirralarini o'rganish orqali - jozibali brend identifikatorini yaratishdan tortib to brend qiymatini yaratish va brendga sodiqlikni rivojlantirishgacha - biz kichik korxonalar brendingdan o'zlarini farqlash, mijozlarni jalb qilish va gavjum bozorda gullab-yashnash uchun qanday qilib strategik vosita sifatida foydalanishi mumkinligini ochib beramiz.*

Kalit so'zlar: *raqobatbardosh, bozor ulushi, tovar xabardorligi, pozitivizm, interpretivizm, ishonchlilik, samaradorlik, oshirish, barqarorlik.*

In today's fiercely competitive business landscape, small businesses face an uphill battle for market share and customer attention. Amidst the cacophony of marketing messages bombarding consumers daily, standing out and carving a niche for a small business can seem like an insurmountable challenge. However, therein lies the power of branding strategies. Effective branding goes beyond mere logo design or catchy slogans; it encapsulates the essence of a company, conveying its values, personality, and promise to its target audience. For small businesses, harnessing the potential of branding can be a game-changer, providing a competitive edge that propels them towards success in the marketplace. Branding isn't complete without a brand strategy to guide your efforts to grow your brand awareness. Social media, influencer marketing, and content marketing are some of the most popular strategies today to increase your brand presence, and many brand awareness statistics speak to their effectiveness. Keep reading more branding statistics on strategy.

This section represents top goals for creating brand content in 2022. According to the survey 1,500 marketers from over 40 countries to indicate their top priorities in creating brand content from most important (1) to least important (8). In the survey, 45% of respondents ranked “increase brand awareness” as the number one priority, giving it top billing among the objectives listed. Brand awareness is the key to driving customers to your business and fostering loyalty. Creating a recognizable brand can help you attract new customers and grow your business. It can also make your brand more memorable and differentiate it from your competitors. Start by creating a strong visual identity for your brand and then consistently apply this branding across all of your [marketing materials](#).

74% of marketers used AI for customer segmentation in 2022. With AI bringing in such positive results in customer profiling, it’s no wonder it’s an unrelentingly growing market worldwide. Branding statistics from Statista show that in 2022, [74% of marketers](#) worldwide used AI to improve their customer segmentation or audience modeling. (Artificial Intelligence (AI) is currently on a meteoric rise, from ChatGPT to Midjourney and more—find out how you can use [AI for small business marketing](#).)

There’s a reason so many airlines, telco companies, and social media networks use the color blue in their branding—[branding statistics on color psychology](#) found that many consumers associate it with trustworthiness and clear communication. Beyond these, blue also expresses reliability and well-being. So, if your brand values include any of these, go ahead and add some blue to your brand identity.

COLOR PSYCHOLOGY IN BRANDING

SOURCE: Towergate Insurance

Fit Small Business

Create More Video Content is an increasingly popular tool for businesses to reach their target audiences. With the rise of digital media, video has become a powerful way to engage customers and build brand awareness. Video is undoubtedly the most effective marketing platform that can increase your brand authority and take your business to a whole new level. Approximately 64% of consumers prefer to watch a video instead of reading a text before making a purchase. Videos can be used to introduce your brand, launch new products, features, or services, and establish a meaningful relationship with your customers. For many businesses, video is the most important element of a branding strategy as it can help you attract and convert more

customers and grow your business. According to statistics, adding a product video to your ecommerce website design can increase conversion rate by 80% or more. It is because video gives your customers a clear idea about your product or service and helps them remember the message. In 2023, if you want to become an expert in your industry, create more video content to engage customers, generate more leads and increase brand awareness. 86% of businesses use video as a marketing-tool. This statistic is a powerful testament to the effectiveness of video as a marketing tool. It shows that the majority of businesses recognize the potential of video to reach and engage their target audience. This statistic is an important reminder that video should be an integral part of any marketing strategy. Video marketers achieve a 54% increase in brand awareness. This statistic is a powerful testament to the effectiveness of video marketing, demonstrating that it can be a highly successful tool for increasing brand awareness. It shows that investing in video marketing can be a great way to get your brand out there and make an impact on potential customers.

In the dynamic landscape of business, small enterprises often find themselves grappling with numerous challenges, from limited resources and fierce competition to changing consumer preferences and market trends. However, amidst these challenges lies an opportunity for small businesses to leverage branding strategies as a powerful tool to enhance their competitiveness and carve out a distinct identity in the marketplace. Throughout this exploration, we have delved into the multifaceted realm of branding, uncovering its transformative potential for small businesses and elucidating key strategies for leveraging branding to drive growth, attract customers, and foster long-term success.

At its essence, branding is not merely about creating visual identities or catchy slogans; it is about shaping perceptions, eliciting emotions, and building meaningful connections with consumers. For small businesses, crafting a compelling brand identity serves as the foundation upon which all branding efforts are built. By defining their unique value proposition, communicating their story, and embodying their core values consistently across all touchpoints, small businesses can establish a distinct identity that resonates with their target audience and sets them apart from competitors.

Central to the effectiveness of branding is the concept of brand equity – the intangible asset that encompasses the value, trust, and loyalty associated with a brand. Building brand equity requires small businesses to deliver on their brand promise consistently, exceed customer expectations, and cultivate positive brand experiences at every interaction. Through this relentless focus on delivering value and building trust, small businesses can enhance their brand's perceived value, command premium prices, and cultivate a loyal customer base that serves as advocates for their brand.

Moreover, branding serves as a powerful tool for positioning small businesses strategically within the competitive landscape. By identifying and articulating their unique selling points, understanding their target audience's needs and preferences, and crafting messaging that resonates with their audience, small businesses can differentiate themselves effectively and establish a competitive edge. Whether by targeting niche markets, emphasizing product quality, or leveraging their brand's heritage and authenticity, small businesses can carve out a distinctive position in the minds of consumers and capitalize on untapped opportunities for growth.

Furthermore, branding plays a pivotal role in fostering brand loyalty and advocacy – two critical components of sustained success for small businesses. Through personalized experiences,

exceptional customer service, and meaningful engagement initiatives, small businesses can nurture lasting relationships with their customers, turning them into loyal brand advocates who champion their brand to others. In an era where word-of-mouth and social proof wield immense influence, the advocacy of satisfied customers can amplify a small business's reach, credibility, and reputation, driving organic growth and expanding its market presence.

In conclusion, the utilization of branding strategies represents a powerful means for small businesses to enhance their competitiveness, attract customers, and thrive in an increasingly crowded marketplace. By cultivating a strong brand identity, building brand equity, strategically positioning themselves, and fostering brand loyalty and advocacy, small businesses can unlock new avenues for growth, differentiation, and sustainability. However, it is essential to recognize that branding is not a one-time endeavor but an ongoing commitment that requires dedication, creativity, and adaptability. As small businesses navigate the complexities of the business landscape, embracing branding as a strategic imperative can serve as a catalyst for success, enabling them to stand out, make an impact, and leave a lasting impression on consumers. Through strategic and purposeful branding, small businesses can seize the opportunities that lie ahead, charting a course towards sustained growth, resilience, and prosperity in the ever-evolving world of business.

REFERENCES

Books and Journals

1. Abbas, J., Mahmood, S., Ali, H., Ali Raza, M., Ali, G., Aman, J., Bano, S. and Nurunnabi, M., 2019. The effects of corporate social responsibility practices and environmental factors through a moderating role of social media marketing on sustainable performance of business firms. *Sustainability*. 11(12). p.3434.
2. Acampora, A. and et.al.,2022. The theoretical development and research methodology in green hotels research: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*. 51. pp.512-528.
3. Al-Ababneh, M.M., 2020. Linking ontology, epistemology and research methodology. *Science & Philosophy*. 8(1).pp.75-91.
4. Alakkas, A. A., Paul, M., Nabi, M. K. and Khan, M. A., 2022. Corporate social responsibility and firm-based brand equity: the moderating effect of marketing communication and brand identity. *Sustainability*. 14(10). p.6033.
5. Ali Abbasi, G., Abdul Rahim, N. F., Wu, H., Iranmanesh, M. and Keong, B.N.C., 2022. Determinants of SME's social media marketing adoption: competitive industry as a moderator. *Sage Open*. 12(1). p.21582440211067220.
6. Alwan, M. and Alshurideh, M., 2022. The effect of digital marketing on purchase intention: Moderating effect of brand equity. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*. 6(3). pp.837-848.
7. Bairagi, V. and Munot, M.V. eds., 2019. *Research methodology: A practical and scientific approach*. CRC Press.
8. Benton, T. and Craib, I., 2023. *Philosophy of social science: The philosophical foundations of social thought*. Bloomsbury Publishing.